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Triple-layered encapsulation of sensitive biomolecules into poly (ϵ -caprolactone) nanofibers using AC electrospaying

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ABSTRACT

The incorporation of sensitive bioactive substances such as proteins or DNA into nanofibers poses a significant problem due to the toxicity of most organic solvents. The main idea of this study is to use alternating current electrospaying to create a suspension consisting of polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) capsules containing a bioactive substance dispersed in a solvent system suitable for a water-insoluble biocompatible polymer. In this suspension consisting of PVA capsules and a chloroform/ethanol mixture, poly (ϵ -caprolactone) (PCL) was dissolved and spun by needle-free electrospinning. The result is a fibrous PCL structure in which PVA capsules containing the bioactive agent are integrated. The PVA capsules protect the bioactive substance from the organic solvents needed to dissolve the PCL. To verify the efficacy of the capsules' protection against chloroform, the green fluorescent protein was first encapsulated into the nanofibers, followed by horseradish peroxidase. Both molecules were shown to retain their bioactivity within the nanofibers.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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1. Introduction

The encapsulation of sensitive bioactive compounds within nanofibers presents a challenge for most biomedical applications since numerous polymers used in the pharmaceutical industry are soluble or spinnable from harsh organic solvents only. This poses a risk to the integrity and stability of the encapsulated sensitive compound.

On the other hand, polyvinyl alcohol (PVA), soluble primarily in water for high degrees of hydrolysis [1], stands out for its non-toxicity and cytocompatibility and is approved for pharmaceutical use [2]. However, high hydrophilicity and partial solubility in air moisture hinder its application in tissue engineering [3, 4]. PVA nanofibers still need to be crosslinked or integrated within a structure of other moisture-proof polymers, such as poly (ϵ -caprolactone) (PCL).

Nano/microencapsulation employs various techniques, including coacervation, emulsification, freeze drying, extrusion, and electrostatic spraying [5, 6]. Most of these techniques have disadvantages of broad diameter distribution and high aggregation rate. Electrospaying avoids these, exhibiting a narrower diameter distribution influenced by voltage, liquid conductivity, and dispensing rate [7]. Unique advantages of electrospaying include “self-dispersion,” preventing droplet aggregation due to the Coulombic repulsion of the charged droplets during the spraying process [7, 8]. However, a drawback involves the need for an oppositely charged electrode, which is particularly challenging for depositing polymers on structured surfaces or liquids. Alternating current (AC) electrical voltages eliminate this requirement [9].

Although AC electrospaying experiments date back several decades, a precise physical description of this method still needs to be improved compared to its DC counterpart [10, 11]. The first publications focused on emulsion formation in liquid-liquid systems. Masayuki Sato, for instance, explored AC-spraying of liquids into immiscible liquid acceptors at low frequencies [11]. In contrast, Guido Gneist and Hans-Jörg Bart [12] investigated AC electrospaying of liquid-liquid systems at high frequencies (30 to 45 kHz). Wang et al. [13] noted similarities between very low-frequency AC spraying and classical DC spraying regarding droplet behavior. Despite this, limited research has been dedicated to AC spraying of polymer solutions. Kessick et al. [14] reported enhanced carboxymethylcellulose coverage on semi-conducting substrates with AC compared to DC, possibly due to reduced surface charge accumulation. This study aims to investigate a strategy to encapsulate bioactive substances in non-water-soluble polymers, such as PCL.

Kurpanik et al. presented the possibility of prolonging protein release by electrospinning from the emulsion [15]. Another possibility to encapsulate sensitive biomolecules is core-shell electrospinning [16, 17]. However, this technique is technologically very challenging, mainly because of maintaining simultaneous dosing of both substances. Another option is spinning from a mixture of two polymers [18, 19] or spinning from suspension [20], but the same solvent system must be used here. Combining the spinning/spraying from two or more needles is also possible [21]. Here, however, droplets/particles are deposited on the surface of the fibers. An overview summary of the different techniques of using nanofibers for drug delivery can be found in [6].

Our study focuses on utilizing low-frequency AC electrospaying to generate a suspension of PVA bioactive substance-containing capsules dispersed in an organic solvent system suitable for PCL. PCL is ultrasonically dissolved in the suspension and spun using needless electrospinning, producing a fibrous structure integrated with PVA capsules containing the bioactive agent. We hypothesize that these capsules shield the bioactive substance from the organic solvents needed to dissolve PCL.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

All the polymers used in the study, namely Poly(vinyl alcohol) with 98% (PVA98) of hydrolysis and an average Mw of 13.000-23.000, Poly(vinyl alcohol) 4-88 “EMPROVE Essential” with an 88% degree of hydrolysis (PVA88) and Poly (ϵ -caprolactone) (PCL) with an average Mn of 80.000, were purchased from Sigma Aldrich (Germany). The solvents, namely chloroform a.g. grade (stabilized with ethanol) and Ethanol absolute a.g. grade, were purchased from Penta Chemicals (Czech Republic); Green Fluorescent Protein (GFP) (a recombinant protein expressed in *E. coli*), 27kDa, peroxidase from horseradish (HRP) Type I, Scopoletin and H₂O₂ were purchased from Sigma Aldrich (Germany). Phosphate buffer saline (PBS) was purchased from P-LAB, a.s., Czech Republic.

2.2. Methods

2.2.1. Preparation of the PVA solution (with and without GFP/HRP)

The PVA solution was prepared by dissolving PVA powder (88% or 98% of hydrolysis) in a distilled water: EtOH solvent system (8:2, w/w) to ensure a final concentration of 8 wt%. The solution was stirred (IKA RCT standard magnetic stirrer, IKA-Werke GmbH & Co. KG, Staufen, GER) at an elevated temperature (heating to 80°C, water bath) for around 48h. Before adding the GFP solution to the PVA, the protein solution was thawed at 8°C for about 1h. Subsequently, 20 μ g of GFP solution was added to 3g of 10% PVA solution (in a PS cuvette). For the encapsulation of HRP, 25 mg of the enzyme was directly added to the 3g of 10% PVA solution. Both suspensions were shaken and then sonicated (GUC 02B, GETI, Opava, CZE) for 2 min to enhance the dispersion. All the cuvette contents were transferred into a 5 ml PP syringe.

2.2.2. Experimental setup for the AC electrospaying

Figure 1 illustrates the experimental setup for the AC electrospaying. The configuration consisted of three components - the polymer dispenser, the ultrasonic bath with the solvent containing the gradually dissolving polymer, and a high-voltage AC power source. The polymer dispenser consisted of a NE-300 syringe pump (New Era Pump Systems, Inc., Farmingdale, NY, USA) mounted on a laboratory lifting platform and a 5-mL polypropylene syringe connected *via* silicone tubing to a 21-gauge (40 \times 0.8mm) blunt needle. The needle was inserted into the cap of a Fisherbrand glass bottle (Fisher Scientific, Leicestershire, UK) perpendicular to the PCL solution so that the distance from the needle tip to the solution was approximately 5 cm. The glass bottle with the polymer solution was placed in a GUC 02B ultrasonic bath

(GETI, Opava, Czech Republic). The sonification frequency was 40 kHz (60 W). The needle was connected to a 10/40 A high-voltage amplifier (Trek Inc., Lockport, NY, USA) supplemented by a GW Instek MFG-2160MF function generator (Good Will Instrument Co., Ltd., New Taipei City, TWN) and a RIGOL DS1074Z-S plus digital oscilloscope (RIGOL Technologies EU GmbH, Gilching, GER). The alternating peak voltage was set at 18.4 kV, and the frequency was set at 3 Hz. Spraying was performed for around 8 h. The dosage was 0.6 ml/hr. The bath temperature was maintained at $20^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 10^{\circ}\text{C}$. The needle diameter was 1.2 mm. The control samples with GFP/HRP added directly to the PCL solution were prepared at the same conditions.

2.2.3. Fabrication of the PVA + GFP/HRP-loaded PCL nanofibrous mats

Electrospinning was performed using a laboratory-scale NANOSPIDER NS 1W500U (Elmarco, Czech Republic) device. The process parameters were set at a temperature of 20°C and a relative humidity of 40%. The potential difference between the electrode and the collector was 50 kV, with a positive charge applied to the electrode and a negative charge to the collector. The distance between the collector and the electrode was 160 mm. The same procedure was subsequently employed to produce modified materials with the presence of GFP/HRP in PVA, and a control sample of pure GFP/HRP was added directly to the PCL solution. The solution of PCL with PVA and GFP/HRP was stored in aluminum foil at 8°C . Subsequently, the solutions were magnetically stirred for around 30 min before electrospinning. The electrospinning of the PCL + PVA + GFP/HRP required a higher potential difference (60 kV) and a lower relative humidity (30%).

2.2.4. Scanning electron microscopy and image analysis

The morphologies of the nanofibrous membranes and the electro-sprayed particles were studied using an electron microscope. A 2 nm layer of gold was sputtered onto the samples using a Bal-Tec SCD 050 Sample Sputter Coater, and the samples were

Figure 1. Schematic of the AC electro spraying apparatus for suspension preparation. The figure illustrates the following components: 1. Laboratory lifting platform, 2. Linear pump with a syringe (3.) holding a stock solution of PVA and GFP, 4. Ultrasonic bath filled with iced water, 5. Vial containing solvent and PCL polymer, 6. Needle with applied AC voltage, 7. High voltage amplifier, 8. Oscilloscope, and 9. Signal generator. The resulting suspension is depicted on the right side of the figure.

observed using a JSM-IT200 scanning electron microscope (JEOL). The fiber diameters were subsequently determined by employing an ImageJ (National Institutes of Health, MD, USA) image analyzer by measuring 100 randomly observed nanofibers selected over various fields of view at a magnification of 5000x. Concerning the particle analysis, the polymer solution was sprayed onto the surface of double-sided adhesive tape attached to a target and then sputtered with 2 nm of gold. Although the use of the fully automated analysis of the particle size applying different image analysis software is expected, such automated approaches often fail to recognize the individual particles, mainly when the image features agglomerates of particles. Thus, this study measured the particle size distribution semi-automatically, applying the classic stereological systematic uniform random sampling (SURS) approach. The SEM image of the particles (magnification of 5000 \times) was divided into 24 equivalent cells applying a grid, with a grid cell size of 8 \times 8 μ m. The fraction of the samples for measurement, f , was then $f=1/p$. The periodicity, p , was chosen at 4. Thus, the total fraction for measurement was 1/4, and the total number of samples was 6. To include randomness in the selection, a random number was generated from 1 to 4 before measurement to serve as the starting point. Finally, a stereological dissector was applied to the individual cells of the grid, and the diameters of all the seen and distinguishable particles were measured.

2.2.5. Dynamic light scattering

Samples for particle measurements by DLS were prepared by AC electrospraying into chloroform for 20 min without PCL by the same method mentioned above. The chloroform bottle was placed in an ultrasonic bath throughout the experiment. The suspension was then transferred to a glass cuvette, and the particle size was measured using a Malvern Zetasizer Nano ZS.

2.2.6. Epifluorescence microscopy

The presence and biological activity of the incorporated GFP were confirmed by observing the treated and untreated samples under an Axio Imager M2 epifluorescence microscope (Zeiss, Germany) equipped with an AxioCam MRm camera and Axio-Vision SE64 Rel 4.9.1 software (Zeiss, Germany). Fluorescence images were obtained at an excitation wavelength range of 445–495 nm, and the observation filter had a long-pass filter wavelength of above 515 nm.

2.2.7. Scopoletin assay

The enzymatic activity of HRP was investigated by scopoletin assay. First, 100 mg of PVA + HRP-loaded PCL Nanofibrous Mats and control mats (HRP-PCL without PVA) were placed into 5 ml tubes filled with 1 ml of PBS and left in the fridge (at 4 $^{\circ}$ C) for 16 h to ensure elution of HRP from the membranes into the solution. Then, a PBS solution of H₂O₂ (3 ml, 2 mM) and scopoletin (10 μ L, 0.8 mM) was mixed and placed in a cuvette to measure fluorescent intensity. Then, either an aliquot of the eluates from nanofibrous mats (50 μ L) or a solution of HRP in PBS (50 μ L, 1 mg/mL) was added to the cuvette and mixed. Fluorescence quenching of scopoletin by H₂O₂

catalyzed by HRP was followed at $\lambda=460\text{ nm}$ ($\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 350\text{ nm}$, at 25° C) using an FLS980 spectrofluorimeter (Edinburgh Instruments, UK).

2.2.8. Fluorescent spectroscopy

Emission spectra of GFP (25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) in distilled water (blue) or chloroform (green) upon excitation at 488 nm. Control emission spectra of distilled water (black) and chloroform (red) alone were also recorded.

2.2.9. Contact angle measurement

The contact angle was measured by online scanning using a Levenhuk DTX 30 USB microscope. A drop of demineralized water was applied to the surface of the layer using a 5-mL pipette with a volume of 10 μL . Subsequently, the whole process was imaged until the drop was completely soaked into the layer.

2.2.10. Statistics

The normality of the fiber diameter data was verified primarily using Shapiro-Wilk's test, and the homoscedasticity was verified by applying Levene's test (significance level of 0.05). The statistical significance of the differences between the nanofibrous layers was analyzed using non-parametric analysis since either the assumption of normality or homoscedasticity was violated. Subsequently, the Mann-Whitney test was performed for the two-sample comparisons, considering a level of $p \leq 0.05$ as statistically significant. The numerical data was expressed as the mean \pm the standard deviation (SD). The fiber diameter data was defined as the median and the interquartile range (IQR = $Q3 - Q1$).

3. Results and discussion

To validate our hypothesis about the protective potential of PVA capsules for sensitive bioactive compounds, careful selection of the encapsulated compound was essential, meeting specific criteria: 1) The compound should possess a sufficiently high molecular weight to prevent diffusion from the polymer capsules into the solvent; 2) It should exhibit sensitivity to organic solvents, resulting in a loss of its bioactivity within them; 3) The method to assess the bioactivity of this compound should be straightforward. Based on this, Green Fluorescent Protein (GFP) and peroxidase from horseradish (HRP) were selected for the encapsulation.

Organic solvents, like chloroform, can disrupt the native structure of proteins by affecting hydrophobic interactions between non-polar functional groups of amino acids [22]. The loss of GFP fluorescence is often used to gauge the denaturation degree [23, 24]. Tsuboyama et al. reported that unprotected GFP exposed to chloroform lost up to 90% of its original fluorescence intensity after 30 min. Therefore, GFP was chosen as a suitable candidate for encapsulation in nanofibers, providing a robust means to test and validate our hypothesis. To confirm GFP denaturation in chloroform, we diluted GFP in either distilled water or chloroform and recorded the emission spectra at 508 nm (Figure 2). In contrast to its emission in water, GFP exhibited no fluorescence in chloroform." We chose horseradish peroxidase as another molecule

Figure 2. Emission spectra of GFP (25 µg/ml) in distilled water (blue) or chloroform (green) upon excitation at 488 nm. Control emission spectra of distilled water (black) and chloroform (red) alone were also recorded.

Table 1. Table of all PVA tested where M_w denotes molecular weight; η_{inh} inherent viscosity; DH degree of hydrolysis; c concentration of PVA in solution; d/f = droplets/fibers. Green colour indicates polymers suitable for the production of fiber-free capsules.

Producer	M_w [kDa]	η_{inh} [mPa.s]	DH[%]	c [%]	d/f
SA-Emprove 4-88	-	3.4-4.6	85-89	8	√/X
SA-Emprove 5-88	-	4.3-5.7	85-89	8	√/√
SA-Emprove 18-88	-	15-20.7	85-89	8	X/√
Sigma Aldrich	13-23	-	98	8	√/X
Sigma Aldrich	31-50	-	87-89	8	√/√
Sigma Aldrich	80-125	-	99	8	X/√

ideal for encapsulation. This cheap, commercially available enzyme loses some of its activity in the organic solvents [25, 26]. Moreover, its bioactivity can be easily monitored through quenching of the emission of its fluorescent substrate, scopoletin, which occurs in the presence of H_2O_2 [27].

PVA with various degrees of hydrolysis was selected to encapsulate the bioactive compounds. This polymer is characterized, in particular, by its low solubility in non-aqueous solvent systems and, therefore, has the potential to provide sufficient protection for the encapsulated substance from the solvents used for dissolving the polymer employed for the formation of the nanofibers [28].

In the search for a suitable PVA for subsequent encapsulation, a detailed study was carried out concerning productivity and particle size. A total of 6 PVA with two different hydrolysis steps with different molecular weights were tested. The most suitable PVA concentration was determined to be 8 wt%. A detailed overview can be seen in Table 1. The emphasis was mainly on droplet formation without associated fibers. It turned out that only PVA with low molecular weights formed droplets without fibers. This is primarily due to the electrical spinning/spraying process, where polymers with lower M_w tend to create more droplets and fewer fibers [29].

PCL dissolved in a mixture of chloroform and ethanol was chosen for the preparation of the nanofibers due to its high cytocompatibility and the long-term experience of its use in the field of tissue engineering [30]. The main idea of this study

was to combine the two polymers mentioned above to create a composite nanofibrous structure, concerning which the primary carrier polymer is PCL with PVA capsules within it containing the bioactive substance. To make the structure, a novel method was developed to prepare the polymer suspension/solution by combining several technologies. AC electrospaying technology was used to prepare the nano/microcapsules. As described in the introductory chapter, this method does not require a counter electrode and is, therefore, suitable for spinning/spraying into the solvent. It was first necessary to determine a PVA with proper molecular weight and degree of hydrolysis to optimize the droplet generation *via* AC electrospaying to the maximum extent. Two PVAs with differing degrees of hydrolysis were selected to generate the droplets. These polymer solutions were subsequently tested for the morphological analysis of the produced samples.

In AC electrospaying, manipulatable parameters include the electrical voltage magnitude, frequency, and signal shape, balancing Maxwell stress $\epsilon E^2/2$ with capillary pressure σ/R at low frequencies [31]. Resonance in an AC field between the input signal frequency and the droplet itself may lead to increased strain, droplet growth, and enhanced detachment, even at lower voltages. Generally, AC electrospaying can be categorized into low-frequency ($f < 10$ kHz) and high-frequency ($f > 10$ kHz) Fields [32] based on the frequency magnitude, with this paper specifically addressing the low-frequency droplet generation method.

A theoretical explanation for low-viscosity drops has been provided by Grigorev [33], who suggested that the time for hydrodynamic drops to regain their spherical shape after stretching must significantly surpass the external electric field's period ($\tau \ll 1/\omega$). The time τ can be estimated as that required for a stretched spheroidal drop to recover its spherical form under the action of surface tension. The center of mass of the half drop moves with constant acceleration under the influence of constant Laplace force, thus determining the following restriction on the drop parameters

$$\tau = \sqrt{\frac{\rho R^3}{3\sigma}} \ll \frac{1}{\omega} \quad (1)$$

where ρ denotes the density of the liquid, R is the radius of the drop, σ is the surface tension of the solution, and ω is the frequency of the external electric field. Maheshwari [31] considered a similar relationship in his research, albeit for a slightly different geometrical arrangement. Substituting values that corresponded approximately with our parameters ($\rho \approx 10^3 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$; $R \approx 10^{-3} \text{ m}$; $\sigma \approx 40\cdot 10^{-3} \text{ N}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$) for each parameter of equation (1), we determined that $f \ll 55$ Hz. The surface tension was determined approximately for water/ethanol at a ratio of 8:2. This simple estimate led us to hypothesize that in order to be able to destabilize a droplet we must apply a frequency in the order of units of Hz. This was confirmed experimentally in our study.

The PVA polymer solution containing the bioactive agent was first 'sprayed' into the PCL solvent. The particles in the polymer solution evinced a tendency to aggregate; the rate of the aggregation of the particles is given by the equation: [34]

$$\frac{dn_k}{dt} = \frac{1}{2} \alpha \beta_{ij} n_i n_j - n_k \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \alpha \beta_{ij} n_i \quad (2)$$

where α is the collision efficiency factor, i.e. a dimensionless quantity that expresses the ratio of the number of collisions involved in the aggregation process to the total number of collisions of the individual particles. The quantities n and β_{ij} denote the density of the individual particles and the collision frequency function, respectively. In our case, collisions due to Brownian motion dominated, where the frequency function is based on Fick's first law with the particle diffusion coefficient given by the Stokes-Einstein equation. The collision rate parameter is described by [35],

$$\beta_{ij} = \frac{2k_B T}{3 \bullet} \left(\frac{1}{r_i} + \frac{1}{r_j} \right) (r_i + r_j) \quad (3)$$

where \bullet denotes the viscosity and r_i and r_j are the radii of the particles. The rate of aggregation can be significantly retarded by reducing the collision factor, for example by adding a surfactant or by increasing the viscosity of the solution. Since the addition of a surfactant could disturb the encapsulation of the active agent and affect the wetting process, it is advisable to increase the viscosity of the solution so as to reduce the frequency function value.

The chloroform container was placed in the ultrasonic bath. It is known that ultrasound is suitable for breaking the attractive forces between particles by increasing their Brownian motion, which acts to break down the aggregated particles [36]. Moreover, ultrasound can be used for the dissolution of polymers. However, care must be taken not to reduce the molecular weight *via* the breaking of the bonds between the monomers due to the application of high energy ultrasonic waves [37]. It is also known from the literature that even repeated sonication should not act to damage the GFP [38]. Therefore, PCL 80k was added to the container of chloroform and ethanol and gradually dissolved during the spraying period. This served to increase the viscosity of the solution and to significantly reduce the degree of particle aggregation. The entire solution/suspension was thus rendered stable and no aggregation nor the sedimentation of the particles was observed over the two weeks in which the solution/suspension was observed. A diagram of the whole of the experiment and an image of the suspension are shown in Figure 1.

The electrostatic spraying process was conducted throughout the dissolution of the PCL. A nanofibrous layer was subsequently prepared from the resulting solution containing the encapsulated bioactive agent *via* needleless electrostatic spinning using a NS 1S500u Nanospider. The machine parameters were selected so that the layer could be sufficiently manipulated. The resulting nanofibrous layer was then subjected to a morphological analysis.

3.1. Characterization of morphology

Our experiments revealed that it is advisable to use low molecular-weight polymers for electrostatic spraying. It is known that the stability of PVA increases with the increasing degree of hydrolysis, where PVA with a high degree of hydrolysis is soluble even in water only at an elevated temperature of 80 °C [39]. Hence, two PVA polymers with low molecular weights and two differing degrees of hydrolysis (88% and 98%) were

selected for the GFP encapsulation. The two polymers at suitable electrospinning concentrations were dissolved in water with ethanol at a ratio of 8:2 and then sprayed onto the target for the SEM analysis.

The micrographs in [Figure 3A and B](#) show that spherical particles with sizes in the range of nano- to micro-meters were obtained in both cases. The histograms illustrate the remarkably different distributions of the two polymers. The PVA98 evinces a narrower relative frequency peak with around 70% of the diameters lying in the range 50-200 nm (mean = 177 ± 229 nm), whereas the distribution of the PVA88 evinces a broader distribution, the mean value of which has shifted towards 500 nm (mean = 413 ± 247 nm). Moreover, the density of the particle coverage of the substrate, which corresponded to the productivity of the solutions, also differed significantly. In the case of the PVA88, various areas of beads were observed to either partially or completely overflow into the fibers. However, no such fibrous structures were observed for the 98% PVA.

The SEM micrographs of the obtained nanofibers were subsequently analyzed. The overall morphologies and histograms of the fiber diameter distributions of all the fabricated layers with and without the addition of GFP are shown in [Figure 4A–E](#). Generally, the fibers obtained had diameters in the range of around 1000 nm. Moreover, the layers without PVA were observed to have considerably finer fibers, while the layers with the added PVA contained a larger number of thick fibers (above 1 μ m). It is also evident that the productivity of the electrospinning process was reduced with the addition of PVA particles to the solution. This also led to a decrease in the density of the obtained nanofibrous meshes. The decrease in productivity and

Figure 3. Histograms of the diameter distributions of the particles produced *via* AC electrospinning from the two polymers – PVA 88 DH (A) and PVA 98 DH (C), intensity weighted particle size distribution of three DLS measurements of samples PVA88 (B) and PVA 98 (D).

Figure 4. Histograms of the fiber diameter distributions ($n=100$) for the produced fibrous materials with representative SEM micrographs (scale bar = 10 μm).

Figure 5. Representative images of the surfaces of the fabricated fibrous materials obtained *via* scanning electron microscopy. PCL (a), PCL+GFP (B), PCL+PVA98 (C), PCL+PVA98+GFP (D), and PCL+PVA88+GFP (E). The scale bar is 1 μm .

increase in the fiber diameters was due mainly to the presence of water in the PCL solution that originated from the PVA solution. Water is a non-solvent for PCL; thus, it acts to prevent its dissolution in wetting solutions and/or causes coagulation.

The fibers made from PVA-free PCL solutions are homogeneous, have predominantly smooth surfaces and have no visible defects. However, the micrographs of the fiber surfaces (Figure 5C and D) show fibers that are covered mostly with spherical particles of several hundred nanometers in size. The coverage of the fibers by these

particles can be described as relatively uniform. No difference is visually apparent between the PVA capsule materials containing and not containing GFP.

Despite the large number of particles on the surface, unfortunately we have not yet been able to determine with the techniques available how effective was the incorporation of the PVA particles inside the PCL fibers. It can also be seen from Figure 6 (bar plot) that in terms of the resulting fiber diameter distribution, the materials produced using PVA88 and PVA98 differed significantly. On the other hand, the intensity of the coverage of the fiber surfaces by the PVA particles was considerably higher for PVA98.

Determining the ratio of particles inside and outside the fibers is very difficult. For this reason, GFP was chosen for its fluorescence properties. However, this method cannot distinguish the particles on the surface of the fibers from those insides.

A certain characterization could be the determination of the release kinetics of biomolecules, where the faster release of the active substance on the surface of the fibers (burst release) could be assumed, while the particles inside are responsible for the long-term sustained release. The HRP experiment may provide a partial answer (see Chapter 3.4). However, here the experiment time was limited to 60 min due to H_2O_2 depletion. For a more detailed determination of this ratio, a more detailed study to determine the kinetics of the release of the active substance will be

Figure 6. Bar plot of the fiber diameters (median and IQR) for the produced fibrous materials (the asterisk indicates statistically significant differences at $p \leq 0.05$).

necessary, where the different phases of the release of the active substance can be clearly separated.

The addition of GFP directly to the electrospinning solution exerted no observable impact on either the electrospinning process or the resulting fiber morphology, as can be seen from [Figure 5 \(B\)](#) and [Figure 6](#) (bar plot). Moreover, no traces of GFP were observed on the PCL fibers. This may indicate that the GFP suspension immediately denatured in the PCL solvent system (i.e. mainly chloroform) and did not affect the polymer solution. Representative images of the fiber surfaces with and without PVA encapsulation are shown in [Figure 5A–E](#).

3.2. Epifluorescence microscopy

The degree of denaturation of the GFP was difficult to measure quantitatively due mainly to the matrix effect of the polymer bilayer, which acts to distort spectrophotometric measurement methods. A further reason comprised simply the lack of a continuous GFP layer in the material. In contrast to studies that considered the direct incorporation of GFP into the nanofiber structure [40–42], the GFP was contained in the PVA particles in our experiment, and constituted around 10% w/w of the resulting fiber material. However, it was shown that the GFP that was added directly to the PCL solution in the system lost its fluorescence properties, whereas the GFP protected in the PVA capsules retained fluorescence even following spinning, as depicted in [Figure 7D and E](#).

[Figure 7](#) presents the epifluorescence microscope images. It is evident that images A, B, and C show no fluorescence, whereas fluorescent spherical particles of a size in the order of micrometer units and less can be observed in images D and E. The fluorescent particles exhibit a similar size and spatial distribution to the PVA particles observed in the electron microscope images. Since these fluorescent particles are not evident on the control layers of the pure PCL or the PCL sample with sputtered PVA particles, it was assumed that they comprise native GFP. The fact that such particles are not observed on the sample for which the GFP was incorporated directly into the

Figure 7. Representative epifluorescence microscopy images. A – negative control (PCL fibers), B – PCL fibers with GFP blended directly into the spinning solution, C – PCL fibers with electro-sprayed PVA98 capsules, D – PCL fibers with GFP incorporated into the electro-sprayed PVA98 capsules, and E - PCL fibers with GFP incorporated into the electro-sprayed PVA88 capsules. The scale bar is 100 µm (10 µm for the magnified micrographs).

PCL (Figure 7B) is indicative of the effectiveness of the procedure and that PVA capsules are capable of sufficiently protecting the GFP molecule exposed to the solvent system of the polymer solution. On the other hand, it is evident that the intensity of fluorescence differs between the PVA88 and PVA98 supplemented layers. Moreover, the gradual decay in the fluorescence of the PVA88-supplemented layers was observed in the epifluorescence microscopy analysis. Together, these observations appear to indicate that the stability of PVA88 is insufficient in terms of protecting the GFP molecule. It is assumed that the reason concerns the gradual diffusion of chloroform into the PVA88 particles, which in turn leads to the denaturation of the GFP in the PCL nanofibers. Subsequently, the stability of GFP in water and chloroform was measured by fluorescence spectroscopy. The emission spectra show a clear degradation of GFP in chloroform and preservation of stability in water.

3.3. Contact angle measurement

From Figure 8, it can be clearly seen that for the PCL/PVA sample, the droplet soaked immediately (valid for both PVA88 and PVA98), while for PCL alone, the whole process took 1 min. From this experiment, it can be clearly concluded that there was a significant increase in the hydrophilicity of the PCL fibers after the application of the PVA capsules.

3.4. Bioactivity of HRP measured by scopoletin assay

The stability of HRP in nanofibrous materials was analyzed by scopoletin assay. Materials with encapsulated HRP in PVA 88 or PVA 98, as well as control membranes (without PVA), were soaked in PBS overnight to ensure the elution of HRP from the nanofibers. Aliquots of the eluate were then added to a solution of fluorescent scopoletin in H_2O_2 . HRP, in its native state, metabolizes scopoletin to a non-fluorescent product, and its bioactivity can thus be easily measured by monitoring the fluorescence decay over time. As seen in Figure 9, adding 50 μ L of PCL-PVA88+HRP membrane eluate resulted in a significant decrease in scopoletin fluorescence. This result indicates

Figure 8. USB microscope images for different droplet collection times. The sample with PVA98 was selected for the experiment. The sample with PVA88 showed the same behavior as PVA98.

Figure 9. Emission of scopoletin in H_2O_2 at 460 nm after the addition of 50 μL aliquots of eluates from PCL+PVA88+HRP (blue), PCL+PVA98+HRP (green) and PCL+HRP (purple). Positive control (red) represents a sample where 50 μL of HRP (1 mg/ml) was added instead of the eluates, negative control (black) represents scopoletin solution in H_2O_2 alone. The table shows the parameters of the “one phase decay” fit, where I_{∞} denotes emission in time $t = \infty$ and K is rate constant.

that HRP was successfully encapsulated into the nanofibrous material and retained its native/active state. In contrast, an aliquot of eluate from the PCL nanofibrous membrane, to which HRP was added without prior encapsulation into PVA, did not affect scopoletin fluorescence. Thus, HRP is very probably denatured in chloroform.

The individual measurements were interleaved using the “one phase decay” function according to the equation $I(t) = (I_0 - I_{\infty}) \exp(-Kt) + I_{\infty}$, where $I(t)$ indicates the emission in time t , I_0 emission in time $t=0$, I_{∞} emission in time $t = \infty$ and K is rate constant. From the individual values, it can be seen that K is the same for both samples with PVA capsules, while the rate of decline for HRP alone is about 2.5 times faster and for HRP in PCL an order of magnitude slower. This suggests a gradual release of HRP from PCL/PVA. However, more detailed studies of the release kinetics will be required to determine the long-term release. The amount of HRP released from PVA98 was approximately 3.5 times lower than PVA88 (determined by I_{∞}). This may be due to the smaller amount of HRP within the PVA98 pattern or the fact that PVA98 has a much poorer water solubility than PVA88 [39]. The effect of the amount of PVA hydrolysis on the leaching of bioactive material from nano/microcapsules will be the subject of our further research. Indeed, this finding could be used for the controlled release of bioactive agents from nanofibers, where the use of PVA with a higher degree of hydrolysis could lead to a slower release of the therapeutic agent from the nanofibers and the use of PVA with a lower degree of hydrolysis could lead to a faster release.

4. Conclusion

For the first time, this study applied the low-frequency AC electrospaying technique to incorporate a sensitive biomolecule in nanofibers *in situ*. A model bioactive molecule, green fluorescent protein (GFP), and horse radish peroxidase (HRP) were

successfully encapsulated within polyvinyl alcohol capsules, followed by their incorporation in polycaprolactone nanofibers using needless electrospinning. The morphological analysis confirmed the presence of uniformly distributed PVA particles on the surface of the fibers. However, more detailed studies of the number of capsules inside and outside the fibers will need to be done.

Further, fluorescence microscopy revealed the presence of fluorescent, nondenatured GFP on the PVA capsule-loaded samples. Moreover, the absence of fluorescence was observed for the samples with GFP incorporated directly in the PCL fibers without encapsulation, suggesting the denaturation of the unprotected GFP in the PCL solvent system. The comparison of PVA with two different degrees of hydrolysis confirmed the hypothesis that PVA88 is not stable enough to protect the GFP sufficiently despite the higher productivity of electrospinning. On the other hand, smaller particles with higher stability were produced from the PVA98.

HRP was employed as another suitable molecule for encapsulation to quantify and confirm the protective function of PVA capsules. Using the scopoletin assay, we demonstrated that both types of PVA capsules prevented HRP denaturation in chloroform.

Although PVA88 did not provide sufficient protection for GFP, the amount of HRP released from PVA88 capsules was significantly higher than that from PVA98. This suggests that even PVA88 may have a sufficient protective function for certain bioactive molecules. Since the varying degrees of hydrolysis of PVA might affect the kinetics of elution of the bioactive compound from the capsules, further research will investigate the benefits of using a particular type of PVA.

In conclusion, this study successfully demonstrated a novel approach to creating complex structures by combining low-frequency AC electrospinning and needless DC electrospinning. The study's findings provide insights into the control of aggregation through the manipulation of the viscosity of the medium. In addition, our study establishes the basis for further investigation of the impact of the degree of hydrolysis and the molecular weight of PVA on the size of the produced nano- and microparticles. Thus, this research serves as a framework for methodological advancements in the field and opens up new horizons concerning the potential use of AC electrospinning in various biomedical applications.

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Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

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Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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